

COMPOSTING AT THE MICA CONDOMINIUM

Proposal by the Environmental Committee

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Contents

What is composting?	2
Benefits of composting	3
About Maryland's Waste Reduction Program	4
Composting vendor comparison	5
Composting at the Mica: Survey results	7
Environmental Committee's recommendation	11
Additional materials	12
→ Compost Crew brochure	
→ List of compostable items	
→ Composting bin size chart	
→ Case study of The Blairs composting program	
→ Case study of Kenwood House composting program	
Sources	13

WHAT IS COMPOSTING?

Composting is a natural process through which organic materials, such as yard trimmings and food scraps from our kitchen, are broken down into a nutrient-rich soil that can be used to nourish landscapes, plants and gardens. Effectively, composting turns waste into a valuable commodity.

Commercial composting refers to large-scale composting designed to handle high volumes of organic waste from businesses, apartment/condo buildings, and other organizations. Organizations contract a composting vendor to pick up the food scraps and other compostable waste generated by their business, customers, or residents, usually once a week. The waste is then transferred to a commercial facility for processing and reuse. The prepared soil, or compost, is delivered to the participating organization and sold to local farms, nurseries, garden centers and municipal landscaping facilities.

BENEFITS OF COMPOSTING

More than 50% of typical municipal garbage in the U.S. consists of organic matter, with food scraps making up the largest portion. The alternative to throwing food scraps in the trash—that is, composting—instead yields numerous environmental, economic, and community benefits.

Environmental

When food waste is sent to a landfill or incinerator, it releases harmful greenhouse gases like methane. Not only do these gases trap heat in the atmosphere and contribute to global warming, they also pollute the surrounding soil, air, and water, posing a health hazard to the humans and animals that inhabit the area.

Composting helps mitigate global warming, and would reduce the Mica's environmental footprint. It would also help cut down on the pollution and health hazards caused by our landfill waste.

Economic

By separating food scraps from the conventional trash stream, we can reduce the volume of trash the Mica generates by more than a third. In the long term, **composting could reduce the size and frequency of trash collection and lower traditional waste hauling costs by 25–40%.**

The offer of a composting service would also make the Mica a more attractive property for current and future residents, and would enhance our reputation as a green community.

Community

Composting our food waste could potentially reduce the Mica's pest problem—a major concern for residents. Currently, organic waste is mixed with non-organic waste and goes down the garbage chute to an open dumpster in the trash room. Rodents are attracted to the rotting smells coming from the dumpster and are easily able to access the trash.

When we deposit our food scraps into a separate, sealable container, the rotting smells which attract the rodents will be eliminated altogether. It will also be nearly impossible for rodents to access the specially designed, latchable plastic bins provided by the composting vendors for food scrap collection.

Additionally, the prepared compost we receive from the vendor could be applied to our landscape and community garden, enriching the soil, improving moisture retention, suppressing plant diseases, and producing more beautiful foliage.

MARYLAND'S WASTE REDUCTION PROGRAM

The state of Maryland is committed to reducing the amount of trash it generates, in law and in practice. **In 2018, Governor Hogan signed off on a sustainable materials management (SMM) policy for Maryland, which emphasizes environmentally and economically sustainable methods to capture and reuse resources. Composting food scraps plays a vital role in this policy.** According to a 2017 study, Maryland currently composts about 20% of its food scraps. The goal is to raise this number to 60% by 2035, at the latest. Maryland also aims to reduce overall greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2030 (relative to 2006 levels). Here, too, diverting food scraps from landfills plays an important role.

Our own **Montgomery County has a goal to recycle 70% of all its waste by the end of 2020**; this includes food scraps and other organic materials. Currently, based on a report by the Sierra Club, the County has only reduced its waste by 40%. Increased composting is a key recommendation from the report in order to reach the County's waste reduction goal, as highlighted in this excerpt:

Montgomery County needs to implement a decentralized approach to food composting: one that combines home and community composting with on-farm and medium-sized operations. This approach would create jobs, reduce private and public sector costs for managing healthy soils and local food production, thereby reinforcing a community culture of sustainability and engaged environmental stewardship.

So, by implementing a composting program, **the Mica will contribute towards Maryland's and Montgomery County's waste and greenhouse gas reduction goals**, thereby fulfilling our civic duty as informed and responsible members of the community.

COMPOSTING VENDOR COMPARISON

The Environmental Committee contacted and received information from three commercial composting vendors: **Compost Crew, Compost Cab, and Key City Compost.**

Compost Crew is a locally owned Montgomery County business based in Rockville, MD. They were founded in 2011 with the vision of eliminating food waste and using it to rejuvenate our natural resources. Today, Compost Crew serves thousands of residential, commercial, and government buildings throughout Washington D.C., Maryland, and Virginia. The Blairs, Mom’s Organic Market, and the Smithsonian are among some of their customers. The company also maintains a presence at the downtown Silver Spring Farmers Market.

Compost Cab started in 2010 and is a partner of DC Public Works. The company has two goals: make it easier for people to compost, and easier for urban agriculture to thrive. They achieve these goals by providing home and commercial composting services, and by partnering with urban farms and community gardens to build soil in the city. In 2016, Compost Cab was awarded the District Sustainability Award by the Department of Energy & Environment.

Key City Compost was founded in 2017 in Frederick, MD. They started by picking up food scraps from friends and family and have grown to a dedicated team that diverts several tons of food waste per week from landfills. Key City’s mission is to expand its composting capacity in Frederick and increase business with HOAs and multi-family units. *They provide a hybrid payment option where a percentage of total costs are covered by the HOA and remaining costs distributed to participating unit owners.*

The table below provides a comparison of the key aspects of these three composting vendors, along with the estimated costs.

No. of units	COMPOST CREW			COMPOST CAB			KEY CITY COMPOST		
	Bin size (gal)	Pickup/ week	Cost/ month	Bin size (gal)	Pickup/ week	Cost/ month	Bin size (gal)	Pickup/ week	Cost/ month
1-3 units	12	1x	\$36				5/unit	1x	\$30/unit
5-10 units	35	1x	\$80	32	1x	\$120	5/unit	1x	\$26/unit
15 units	65	1x	\$115				64	1x	\$120

50 units	4 x 65	1x	\$326				4 x 64	1x	\$450
Entire building	5 x 65	2x	\$543				4 x 64	2x	\$800
PROCESS	Residents collect scraps at home (freeze scraps or store in small trash can or countertop container). They deposit the scraps EITHER in a 12 gallon bin in the trash room on their floor OR directly in a central bin in the upper garage. If floor trash room bins are utilized, janitorial staff will transfer contents to central bin in garage. Company collects contents of large central bin every week and swaps bin liners.			Residents collect scraps at home (freeze scraps or store in small trash can or countertop container). They deposit the scraps in a 32 gallon bin in the upper garage. Company collects contents of large bin every week.			Model 1 provides 5 gallon bins to each interested unit. Company staff “run each floor” to collect bins from participating residents and provide them with fresh bins every week. Model 2 utilizes 64 gallon bins located in a central location (upper garage). Company collects contents of large central bin every week and swaps bin liners as well as bins.		
TRAINING	1 hour Zoom training and Q&A; promotional and educational materials, including list of compostable items. Subsequent trainings available at \$99/hour.			Tailor-made digital campaign to maximize participation; zero waste training.			Zoom training at launch. Quarterly Q&A available on request.		
COMPOST DELIVERY	2x/year 4 cubic feet total			2x/year 1 cubic feet total; more available at additional cost			As much as we request (as long as the amount is “reasonable”).		
OTHER COSTS & SERVICES	Small kitchen bins for individual units available (cost depends on size/quantity) If opting for trash room bins on each floor, one-time purchase of 12 gal bins at \$50.00 each + compostable liners. Monthly food scrap weight report at \$4/month (optional). This would provide stats for waste being diverted from landfills and help reduce waste hauling costs. It could also be used to further market Mica as a green community.			\$60 setup fee. Compostable liners for collection bin.			If model 1 is selected, where bins are collected from individual units, any time spent on-site above the cut-off time (usually 2 hours) incurs \$20/hour. Monthly food scrap weight report. This would provide stats for waste being diverted from landfills and help reduce waste hauling costs. It could also be used to further market Mica as a green community.		

COMPOSTING AT THE MICA: SURVEY RESULTS

In order to gain an understanding of residents' attitudes towards and willingness to participate in a composting program, the Environmental Committee conducted a survey at the Mica over the course of a month. We provided the survey to residents by email and via paper copies in the mail room. **We received almost 50 responses, or about one third of the building's units, which we consider a very successful outcome.**

- **Motivation**

The majority of residents who completed the survey (77.8%) say they are familiar with the concept of composting, and 16.7% are interested in learning more. So, **motivation to compost food scraps ranks high among the Mica's residents.**

However, most residents (65.9%) have not participated in a composting program before. This indicates that education and training will be critical to the success of any composting program we implement.

Have you participated in a composting program before, or done your own composting?

- **Implementation**

In terms of implementation, there are three ways in which a composting program at the Mica could work:

1. **Residents collect their food scraps in a vendor-provided 5 gallon bin that is picked up directly from their unit once a week.** (NOTE: At the time of the survey, we were not aware of this option so it was not included in the survey)
2. **Residents deposit their food scraps in a compost bin located in the trash room on their floor.** Several times a week, the janitorial staff takes these bins down to the upper garage to deposit the contents in a larger central bin. The contents of the large bin are picked up by the composting vendor once a week.
3. **Residents deposit their food scraps directly in a large central bin located in the upper garage.** The contents of this bin are picked up by the composting vendor once a week.

Naturally, most residents would prefer the more convenient option 2:

If we had a composting bin in the trash room on each floor, would you be willing to discard your food scraps and other biodegradable waste there, similar to how we do recycling?

However, a majority of residents also said they would be willing to bring their food scraps to the garage (the Yes and Maybes combined represent over 75% of total responses):

Count of What if the composting bin was situated at the garage level? Would you be willing to bring your food scraps and other biodegradable waste downstairs, similar to how we dispose bulk trash?

This shows us that **residents are genuinely interested in composting**, even if the implementation causes them the minor inconvenience of bringing their organic waste to the garage once or twice a week.

- **Cost**

We posed the question to residents about how they would prefer that a composting service at the Mica was paid for. While the majority of respondents indicate that they would prefer this to be an item in the building's budget—similar to how recycling and trash pick-up is treated—almost 41% would be willing to pay for it individually. **This again shows that motivation to compost at the Mica is high!**

Count of Would you be willing to pay a monthly fee of \$10-\$15 for a community composting service, or would you prefer that composting be covered as a line item budget approved by the MICA, similar to recycling and trash pick-up?

- **Most engaged Mica floors**

Looking at a distribution of survey responses by floor shows that **there is widespread interest in composting throughout the building**. We received at least 1 response from each floor with the exception of the 2nd floor; between 2-4 responses from each of nine floors; and greater than 5 responses from each of three floors, with the 14th having the most respondents (n=7) and the 10th floor a close second (n=6).

- **Addressing concerns**

About 16% of respondents mentioned concerns about pests and smells, as well as fitting composting into the existing Mica budget to **avoid an increase in condo fees**, which are the highest in the area.

→ Pests & Smells

As we mentioned in the “Benefits of composting” section, the **composting bins provided by the vendors are fully latchable/sealable, so that odors are trapped inside**. This factor itself will serve as a deterrent to pests. All three vendors also assured us that their **customers have never complained about a rodent being able to enter a latched bin**.

In fact, our present trash disposal system is responsible for the extremely foul odors in the upper garage, which are a primary factor for attracting pests. So, reducing the amount of organic waste disposed through the trash chute would actually alleviate the odor problem. **If we are able to implement a composting service throughout the building and eliminate food waste from the trash chute entirely, that could very well be the answer to our pest problem.**

→ Costs

We would defer to management and the board on the issue of cost. However, as indicated in the “Composting vendor comparison” section, the monthly costs for composting services are not high. Additionally, **the cost of composting could be off-set by a reduction in the volume of trash generated by the building and a corresponding reduction in waste hauling costs**. Also, as mentioned before, one vendor (Key City Compost) offers a hybrid payment option where a percentage of total costs are covered by the HOA and remaining costs distributed to participating unit owners.

● Positive feedback

We received a number of positive comments in the feedback section of the survey. Some of these are listed below:

- “I appreciate the initiative and I would love to compost.”
- “I hope it gets approved.”
- “Really hope we do this! I am on board for however the building chooses to implement.”
- “Super duper excited for this!!!”
- “I know very little about composting but appreciate all that it offers in terms of sustainability, green living, reducing our carbon footprint, etc. - I am all for that and would love to see MICA move in that direction. I'm assuming that if logistics were taken care of following best practices for composting in a multi-unit, multi-level building (e.g. controlling smell, pest control, etc.), then it would be a helpful system to implement. Thanks, Environmental Committee, for your work on this!”

ENVIRONMENTAL COMMITTEE'S RECOMMENDATION

Pilot Composting Program

Based on our extensive research as well as the results of the resident survey, the Environmental Committee recommends running a pilot composting program at the Mica before rolling out a building-wide program.

Recommended vendor

We recommend using the services of **Compost Crew**. They are a well-established local vendor with many years of experience servicing multi-unit buildings, including our neighbors The Blairs. They also provide the largest number of bin sizes, allowing us to scale up the program at any time.

35 Gal

Pilot Program Implementation

We recommend starting the program with **one 35-gallon bin in the recycling room in the upper garage**. This medium-sized bin would be able to **fit food scraps from about 10 units and cost only \$80/month**. If the bin is consistently full at the end of the pilot period, that will indicate that a greater number of units are interested in composting, allowing us to scale up accordingly.

While most residents mentioned in the survey that they would prefer to have the composting bin on their own floor, we think the garage placement will allow us to begin the program immediately and provide all who are willing a convenient way to compost. If we see adoption increase either quickly or over time, we can look into a floor-by-floor implementation.

Our recommendation means residents will have to travel to the ground floor with their food scraps. Based on our research and vendor-provided information, there are a few tips residents can follow: freezing their scraps in a tupperware box and bringing it downstairs once a week, or storing their scraps in a small lidded bin at home and bringing that down once a week (or as often as they prefer). Compost Crew is able to provide small bins for home use at an additional cost.

We would also like to recommend inviting the vendor to a monthly board meeting for a 30-minute Q&A. This way, both the board's and residents' additional questions can be addressed directly. Once the program is approved, we will work with our chosen vendor on a timeline for the implementation, which would include training and educational sessions, distribution of instructional materials, etc.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

- [Compost Crew brochure](#)
- [List of compostable items](#)
- [Composting bin size chart](#)
- [Case study of The Blairs composting program](#)
- [Case study of Kenwood House composting program](#)

SOURCES

- [Commercial Composting Guide, Sierra Club, Washington DC Chapter](#)
- [Recommendations for Achieving Zero Waste in Montgomery County, Sierra Club, Montgomery County Chapter](#)
- [Waste Reduction and Resource Recovery Plan, Maryland Department of Environment](#)
- [Strategic Plan to Advance Composting, Compost Use, and Food Scraps Diversion in Montgomery County, Maryland Department of Environmental Protection](#)
- [Reducing the Impact of Wasted Food by Feeding the Soil and Composting, EPA](#)

